

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING AS A WAY TO CHANGE PERSONAL AND BEHAVIORAL FEATURES

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Abstract. *The development of autopsychological competence is the main goal of social psychology training. This article classifies trainings according to the structural aspects of a person's psychology that they affect. Furthermore, the idea of psychological influence and its different manifestations in relation to training methods are examined. The author also provides viewpoints on assessing training efficacy. The paper also emphasizes the intricate paths that training methods are taking in the modern world.*

Keywords: *individual training, perception, communication, psychological influence, social-psychological training, and training.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ТРЕНИНГ КАК СПОСОБ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ЛИЧНОСТНЫХ И ПОВЕДЕНЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК

Аннотация. *Развитие аутопсихологической компетентности является основной целью обучения социальной психологии. В статье классифицируются тренинги в соответствии со структурными аспектами психологии человека, на которые они влияют. Кроме того, рассматривается идея психологического воздействия и его различные проявления в отношении методов обучения. Автор также приводит точки зрения на оценку эффективности обучения. В статье также подчеркивается сложный путь, по которому идут методы обучения в современном мире.*

Ключевые слова: *индивидуальное обучение, восприятие, коммуникация, психологическое воздействие, социально-психологическое обучение, обучение.*

It was not until the late 1980s and early 1990s that the phenomenon of social-psychological trainings made its way into the field and practice of Russian psychology.

The first local researchers to test and implement training techniques derived from Western science were representatives of the Leningrad school of psychology. Before that, the concept of training was primarily studied through translated foreign literature, with Karl Rudeschtam's work "Group Psychotherapy," which was translated and published in 1990, being particularly significant for Russian scholars. Some experts believe that L. Petrovskaya's 1982 research served as the theoretical foundation that shaped the methodological basis of social-psychological training in Russia. Furthermore, the 1989 book "Social-Psychological Training" by V. Zakharov and N. Khryashova is regarded as the first to offer local training strategies and tactics from a useful standpoint.

The field still has many conflicting interpretations and unresolved inconsistencies because of its comparatively short history. The following is an explanation of the various forms of social-psychological training: this kind of group psychological impact offers the chance to quickly expand information, build or develop critical social-psychological viewpoints, and improve interpersonal communication abilities.

Advantages of Group Training

Group-based training provides the opportunity to utilize the beneficial aspects of all group psychological methods. Participants express their viewpoints, discuss opposing opinions, critically reflect on ideas, and reassess their own actions and behaviors.

Training Outcomes

The highest level of autopsychological competence growth among participants is the training's most successful result. As the transfer of information from one participant to another is the fundamental difference of training methods, S.I. Makshanov highlights that such training should be described based on the notion of psychological influence.

Psychological influence can be classified as partial or global based on the extent of its impact on the human psyche. A person's psyche may change in certain ways as a result of partial influence. Conversely, global influence describes dynamic shifts in a variety of psychological categories, including an individual's motivational zone, self-esteem, and fundamental beliefs. Intentional (planned) or unintended (unplanned) psychological influence depends on the training goal. The goal of effective training is to give planned influence in a manner that meets the developmental needs of the learner.

As a "side effect" of the training, unintended influence could happen (e.g., a person experiencing lower motivation owing to stress or, conversely, obtaining unanticipated new motivation).

By modeling particular scenarios and modifying participants' emotional reactions and behavioral patterns accordingly, "training-rehearsals" help achieve these objectives. The advantages of this system are further enhanced by the group training structure. Participants debate different, occasionally opposing viewpoints, defend their own opinions, provide and accept helpful criticism, and examine themselves. High levels of autopsychological competence are formed as a result of such training or a sequence of trainings. S.V. Kruglik defines autopsychological competence as the capacity to engage in self-development and to assess and manage one's own psychological resources. It consists of the following parts:

- cognitive (consciousness and understanding),
- emotional control,
- Conduct,
- as well as motivational-axiological (values and motivation based on purpose) elements.

"Personal growth trainings" are trainings that focus on personal transformation.

A.K. Pavlova claims that these trainings are distinct from others because they are intended to build the self's structure rather than only enhance social skills. However, as inner traits eventually show themselves in behavior, personal growth trainings also aid in behavioral development.

Social psychology training comes in a variety of forms, including:

- Trainings in communication that are intended to enhance the ability to communicate verbally,
- Trainings in emotional competency assist individuals in comprehending and efficiently controlling their emotions.
- Trainings in assertiveness (leadership), which emphasize boosting self-esteem and breaking down social boundaries,
- The purpose of gender trainings is to dispel myths and preconceptions based on gender.

Innovative Instruction and the Efficiency of Social-Psychological Instruction

The goal of creative training is to help people become more creative. In this sense, social-psychological training is seen as a successful strategy for influencing and improving social-individual interactions. In reference to the efficacy of social-psychological training, S.V.

Kruglik states that autopsychological competence is the capacity of an individual to examine and modify their own psychological resources and to grow as a person. The researcher claims that autopsychological competency is made up of the following essential elements:

- Mental,
- emotional control,
- behavioral, as well as
- Axiological and motivational elements.

As a result, training can be structured in a variety of ways that affect the individual's worldview and psychological characteristics. Trainings focused on personal change are essentially "personal growth trainings," according to A.K. Pavlov. Unlike previous trainings, these focus more on growing the self's structure than on enhancing functional skills. However, because a person's actions eventually reflect the features they have formed, such trainings also have a direct impact on behavioral characteristics. Various typologies can be used to categorize social psychology trainings. Trainings in communication, for instance, can be identified as a distinct category. The goal of these trainings is to improve both verbal and nonverbal communication abilities. The communicative sub-competence is where autopsychological competence is most evident. Gender trainings, according to A.K. Pavlov, are a separate category since they emphasize the development of an individual's identity and behavioral parameters according to gender identification. These trainings aid in dispelling false gender perceptions and challenging conventional gender norms. Creative training is one of the newer forms of training.

The goal of these trainings is to release each person's creative potential. According to this viewpoint, even if these practices are frequently linked to art therapy, their distinctive use of standard training approaches sets them apart from traditional training methods.

Social-psychological trainings can also be classified based on psychological influence strategies. Among these are:

- the developmental strategy (which aims to accelerate one's potential for self-development),
- the manipulative strategy (which relies on subconscious stimulation),
- and the imperative strategy (which offers short-term impact).

Depending on the audience and training objectives, trainers frequently combine these tactics in practice. However, there are several difficulties with contemporary training.

One of these is the increasing number of people who pose as trainers and may provide subpar or even dangerous trainings despite having insufficient psychological training and expertise.

The process of digitization is another urgent concern. Nowadays, a lot of trainings are conducted online. But because real-time involvement, which is a crucial component of training, is greatly diminished in an online setting, this format has frequently been criticized for its poor efficacy. To increase the efficacy of online trainings, it is imperative to design particular techniques. Researchers differentiate between the effects at the individual, group, and organizational levels when assessing training outcomes. The evaluation model created by D.L. Kirkpatrick is among the most well-known and evaluates:

- responses of participants,
- The level of education,
- alterations in behavior, and
- overall outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, social-psychological training has become a widely utilized tool in contemporary society, with a wide range of programs focusing on areas such as communication, gender issues, creativity, leadership, and more. When properly designed and implemented, these training programs offer significant psychological benefits to participants. However, if applied incorrectly, they can lead to undesirable outcomes. It is crucial that these programs are based on scientific principles and led by qualified professionals. Programs that fail to produce the intended psychological effects, or that result in harmful outcomes, cannot be considered successful.

Therefore, it is imperative to assess the effectiveness of these trainings by evaluating the degree of psychological impact they have on participants, ensuring that the desired outcomes are achieved.

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